

MICROLEARNING IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Abstract. Microlearning offers an effective approach to foreign language education by delivering content in concise, manageable segments that fit into short-term study schedules. This article examines the impact of microlearning on language acquisition, focusing on its ability to enhance vocabulary acquisition, pronunciation, and grammar understanding through methods like flashcards, brief videos, and interactive quizzes. By fostering regular engagement and adapting to learners' busy routines, microlearning addresses the challenges of traditional, time-intensive language study.

Keywords: accessibility, flexibility, microlearning, vocabulary acquisition, pronunciation, and grammatical understanding.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of digital technologies has transformed educational practices, prompting a shift toward more flexible and learner-centered approaches. Microlearning, defined as the delivery of content in small, focused units, has emerged as a method in foreign language education. Unlike traditional, lengthy lessons, microlearning offers brief, targeted learning experiences that can be easily integrated into daily life. This approach is particularly appealing in today's fast-paced environment, where learners often face time constraints and seek more efficient ways to acquire new skills. Microlearning's potential to enhance language acquisition lies in its capacity to promote consistent engagement and strengthen learning through repetition and varied formats, such as flashcards, short videos, and interactive exercises. These micro-units allow for instant learning, enabling students to engage with language content at their own pace and in contexts that are immediately relevant, thus supporting greater personalization and autonomy. However, while the popularity of microlearning is growing, empirical evidence on its effectiveness, particularly in the context of short-term foreign language study, remains limited. This article is devoted to filling this gap by investigating the methodological effectiveness of microlearning in foreign language education. How microlearning strategies can support vocabulary acquisition, pronunciation, and grammatical understanding, will be investigated, and addresses the challenges and considerations in implementing these approaches will be addressed.

METHODS

This research employed qualitative and secondary data analysis methods to highlight the role of microlearning in foreign language education. The study focused on analyzing existing scientific researches to assess the effectiveness of microlearning strategies on language learning outcomes. To achieve this, a range of previous research studies was reviewed, focusing on those that examined microlearning in the context of language acquisition. The qualitative approach involved a thematic analysis of selected studies, which were identified based on their relevance to microlearning in foreign language education. No new primary data were collected; instead, existing research findings were synthesized to draw conclusions about the effectiveness of microlearning. The studies included were chosen for their focus on key areas such as vocabulary acquisition, pronunciation improvement,

grammatical understanding, and learner engagement within microlearning contexts. Furthermore, secondary data analysis allowed for a comprehensive review of how microlearning has been implemented across various educational settings and its impact on learners. By examining the literature, patterns and themes were identified, including the benefits and challenges of using microlearning in short-term language study.

RESULTS

The theoretical part of the research indicates that microlearning, while still emerging in formal education, particularly in higher education, has been recognized by several studies for its convenience and time efficiency (Javorcik & Polasek, 2019). Research has shown that microlearning can positively influence information retention by 18-20% (Giurgiu, 2017; Mohammed et al., 2018). Important contributions to this field have been made by Buchern and Hamelmann (2010), who established key principles for micro content design, emphasizing that microlearning units should be self-contained, easy to understand, focused, and centered on specific topics or ideas. However, most existing studies have predominantly focused on lecture-based subjects, with relatively few exploring practice-oriented disciplines (Avramenko, 2019; Rogovaya, 2017). This gap highlights the need to examine the effectiveness of microlearning in foreign language instruction. An analysis of pedagogical and psychological literature supports microlearning as a practical and timely strategy, rooted in cognitive psychology, which asserts that working memory has limited capacity and attention spans are generally short, ranging from 8 to 20 minutes. Consequently, smaller, more digestible pieces of information are more effectively processed, whereas large volumes of content can overwhelm the learner, reducing engagement and hindering the learning process (Giurgiu, 2017). This is particularly relevant for millennial learners, who are characterized by shorter attention spans and fragmented perception. When designing microlearning content, it is recommended that each unit should not exceed 15-20 minutes, though this can vary depending on factors such as the unit's objective, format, and the learner's language proficiency level (Rogovaya, 2017). In addition to the concise nature of microlearning units, the repetition of content over time is crucial for effective information retention. Research dating back to the 19th century has explored the phenomenon of forgetting, with findings suggesting that material should be reviewed at various intervals, such as 20 minutes, 1 hour, 9 hours, 1 day, 2 days, and up to 31 days post-initial learning (Marre & Dros, 2015). This concept is particularly significant in language learning, where repeated exposure to vocabulary and grammar in progressively challenging contexts is essential for mastery. A key advantage of microlearning is its ability to facilitate spaced repetition and content review, making it accessible anytime and anywhere, such as during idle moments in transit or while waiting, through mobile apps, messaging platforms, and social media.

DISCUSSION

Micro content is primarily multimedia in nature and offers a high degree of visual engagement, providing multiple modes of perception. This polymodality, combined with the high accessibility and mobility of microlearning, supports a learner-centered approach. Micro-units allow learners to learn content at their own pace, adapting to individual language proficiency levels and personal learning styles. Microlearning is beneficial for both teachers and students; teachers can easily keep the content updated, and students find it more manageable. According to the survey held during previous researches, 88% of students

reported that micro tasks are more user-friendly and effective, and 62% preferred completing a 15-20-minute task daily over doing a one- to two-hour activity once or twice a week. These findings were consistent with observations from the initial stage of our study, where students were given a choice between several short tasks and one longer activity with equivalent total workload. Notably, 89% of students opted for the shorter tasks. However, it is important to recognize that breaking down educational material into smaller units does not simplify the teaching process; rather, it introduces complexity by integrating various methods, approaches, and techniques (Bruck et al., 2012). Each micro unit that a student engages with is part of a larger macrostructure that must be strategically planned by the instructor. In short, the findings from the research highlight several advantages of microlearning: accessibility, flexibility, psychological feasibility, relevance to time constraints, potential for spaced repetition, and visibility, as well as its alignment with a learner-centered approach and ease of updating materials.

CONCLUSION

The analysis of microlearning's role in foreign language education demonstrates its effectiveness in supporting language acquisition. The evidence suggests that microlearning, with its brief and focused content delivery, helps improve vocabulary learning, pronunciation, and grammatical skills. Its flexibility allows learners to integrate language practice into their daily routines, making it a practical option for busy schedules. Despite these advantages, challenges remain. High-quality content and engaging learning activities are crucial for maximizing the benefits of microlearning. The effectiveness of this approach can be influenced by how often the content is used, how well it is designed, and the feedback provided to learners. In summary, microlearning offers an alternative to traditional language learning methods, particularly when time and accessibility are limited. Further research should address current limitations, improve implementation strategies, and conduct research on how microlearning can be fitted to various educational needs. This will help educators make the most of microlearning's potential to enhance language learning.

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